

**Beyond Science and Decisions:
From Problem Formulation to Dose-Response.
Report from Workshop III**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarizes the results of the third in a series of three workshops conducted to evolve the methodologies and to address the issues raised by the National Research Council of the National Academies report entitled *Science and Decisions: Advancing Risk Assessment* (NRC, 2009). Conducted under the aegis of the Alliance for Risk Assessment (ARA), the workshops were led by a science panel designed to be balanced and reflective of a range of affiliations, perspectives and expertise. Three rapporteurs took notes and summarized Workshop III for this Executive Summary and Report, which was then reviewed by the science panel.

The workshop was organized around three cross-cutting topics: problem formulation, use of mode of action information, and endogenous/background exposure. Six new case studies, identified by the panel to address important gaps in methodology, were presented for panel input on the utility of the methods to address specific problem formulations and consideration of areas for additional development. In addition, case study authors provided short updates for panel feedback on five case studies that had been substantially modified since their presentation at the second workshop. A framework for organizing the case study methods that was developed by panel members and workshop participants was presented and briefly discussed. The meeting concluded with a discussion of next steps.

Several overarching themes emerged from the workshop discussions. This Executive Summary first presents the broad overarching conclusions and then key conclusions that emerged from each of the three themes addressed during the workshop, additional methods needed, and next steps. The Workshop Report provides further detail.

Overarching Conclusions

- A wide range of problem formulations or decision contexts exist for which different dose-response analysis techniques are needed.
- A wide range of dose-response approaches exist that apply increasingly data-informed methods.¹ These approaches, when adequately supported by relevant chemical-specific and biological data, have the potential to additionally refine estimates of hazard.
- There is a benefit to bringing stakeholders together to share and develop a repository of methods as a basis to further consider the issues raised by the NRC report.
- It would be useful to develop an ongoing process to additionally develop the workshop series, expand the repository of methods, and continue to address relevant issues.

¹ There was some disagreement among the panel members about the best wording for approaches that are not the default. Some members emphasized the use of “increasingly data-informed approaches,” while others, noting that there is a biological basis for defaults, preferred the use of terms such as “chemical-specific,” “model-specific,” or “mode of action specific.” However, because such terms do not capture the idea of a continuum of approaches reflecting increasing degrees of understanding of how the chemical behaves, this report primarily uses the term “increasingly data informed.” That term is not intended to imply an absence of data-informing default approaches.

- There is a need for increased communication about current available methods and documentation, including documents developed within regulatory agencies on problem formulation and published national and international criteria on the application of the “increasingly data-informed methods.”
- Overall, it is important for risk assessors to explain the criteria that were applied in the choice of a particular dose-response or risk assessment approach, as well as how the dose-response results will be incorporated into a risk management decision.
- Value of information (VOI) analysis is important for determining the level of effort expended in an assessment and for matching the information needs to the specific decision context.

Key Conclusions on Main Themes

Problem Formulation

- Problem formulation is of critical importance and should guide decisions on what questions to ask and what level of analysis is appropriate. Informal (qualitative) value of information analysis is particularly useful during the problem formulation step to help focus resources on issues and analyses that are “fit for purpose” for the decision to be made.
- Several important aspects of problem formulation were noted together with the importance of addressing these aspects early in the process. These early tasks include defining the risk management goals, developing a process for communication of the plan to stakeholders and providing for stakeholder engagement, and communication between risk managers and risk assessors. From the technical perspective, it was noted that early assimilation of an overview of the data as a basis for identifying critical issues can markedly increase efficiency of the risk assessment process by informing the appropriate focus of the assessment.
- Problem formulation should consider such topics as the type of decision, what is at stake (e.g., are there large financial consequences or large exposed populations, either of which would increase the importance of the assessment), and the appropriate focus, depending on information available.
- Calculating a risk-specific dose for a noncancer endpoint can be useful for multiple reasons in addition to the cost-benefit application noted by NRC (2009). The appropriate approach to dose-response analysis should consider how closely the measured or predicted exposure approaches an estimate of a safe dose. Calculating a risk-specific dose can be useful if the range of exposures imply doses that are close to a safe dose estimate but is of much less interest if the measured or estimated exposure is well below a safe dose.
- Tiered approaches can be helpful for ensuring efficient use of resources, with the assessment proceeding to the next tier only if needed to inform the risk management decision to be made. Similarly, the problem formulation can help to determine which of a series of increasingly informed approaches is needed for the assessment in order to support a decision, depending on the nature and potential impact of the decision.

Mode of Action (MOA)

- Depending on the risk assessment needs identified in the problem formulation, increasingly data-informed approaches that incorporate information on MOA can be applied. These include generic predictive approaches in early tiers of assessment and more chemical-specific derivations in later tiers. Incorporation of information on MOA permits more predictive and accurate quantitation of dose-response in humans, including potentially sensitive populations. Thus, MOA is important for a variety of tiers of assessments.
- There is a need for increased understanding in the risk assessment community of the basis for defaults and their underlying assumptions as a basis for comparison with increasingly data-informed approaches.
- Transparency in the degree of uncertainty (both qualitative and quantitative) associated with increasingly data-informed dose-response analysis methods is critical in increasing the risk assessment community's understanding of how information on mode of action is useful for more accurately predicting risk in the human population. Such transparency will help risk assessors understand the different types and degrees of uncertainty associated with different analysis methods and aid in the choice among these different methods.
- It is important to have a consistent and rigorous set of criteria to inform decisions about appropriate consideration of increasingly data-informed approaches.
- Understanding of the biology underlying evaluation of health effect data has evolved since the early days of risk assessment, leading to less of a need for a reliance on statistically derived defaults. An understanding of the evolving biology is needed in evaluating risk assessment methods; statistical analyses need to be coupled with biological understanding.
- There is a need to design standard toxicity studies to collect information about MOA to complement that about hazard identification. To help facilitate the utility of testing, it would be useful for assessments to state the type of information needed to remove or reduce identified uncertainties. Increased transparency in uncertainties associated with a range of increasingly data-informed approaches will also contribute to increasing the relevance and predictive ability of collected information, by encouraging researchers to target their work towards those uncertainties, and in helping risk assessors consider the weight of evidence and implications of the uncertainties associated with different approaches.

Endogenous/Background

- Clarity in definitions and use of terminology is needed. Different considerations are needed to address endogenous exposures (exposures that are internally generated as a result of normal metabolic processes) and background exposure (those that may result from sources other than the subject of the risk assessment).
- There is no single clear risk assessment approach for dealing with endogenous exposure, but some key considerations and issues can be identified. The implications of endogenous exposure need to be considered in the context of evaluating a health-related endpoints or

effects. In particular, a key issue is whether the endogenous exposure is close to a dose that would cause an effect. Population variability in endogenous levels also needs to be considered, but high variability alone is not a sufficient reason to conclude that exogenous exposure is trivial; the endogenous exposure needs to be considered in the context of how far it is from a threshold (or from an exposure of concern). The impact of the total dose from both endogenous and exogenous sources also needs to be considered.

- Considerations relevant to increasing degree of conservatism as a basis for public health protection (i.e., science policy) or feasibility of risk management should be transparent and distinguished from those which are fully science based.

Additional Methods Needed

The panel briefly discussed what additional methods are needed. This list is not exhaustive, but captures some initial thoughts on methods that would be useful to add in follow-on work.

- More is needed on combined exposures. There is a recently published WHO IPCS framework report that will be helpful in providing and framing appropriate case studies.
- A case study on value of information would be useful.
- A case study that illustrates an entire risk assessment, from problem formulation to conclusion, would be useful.
- A case study on *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation would be useful. ILSI is doing work in this area.
- The ARA Dose-Response Framework for case studies could point to examples outside of this compendium of case studies.

Next Steps

Several next steps were recommended. These include:

- Publication of a peer-reviewed journal article capturing key results and lessons learned from the workshop series, illustrated by case studies (e.g., in text boxes), and pointing the reader to the framework for organizing the dose-response methods and case studies.
- Developing an evergreen approach, including panel review of methods on an annual or semi-annual basis, leading to updating the framework for organizing the dose-response methods and case studies.
- Approaches for further dissemination of the workshop results to the risk assessment community, including presentations at professional society meetings and to influential individuals and groups.

INTRODUCTION

Workshop Scope and Objectives

This workshop series was designed to extend the discussions initiated by the National Research Council report *Science and Decisions: Advancement of Risk Assessment* (NRC, 2009) in a multi-stakeholder format in support of developing a practical, solution-oriented, risk assessment methods compendium. The methods compendium is intended for use by risk managers and scientists in a variety of venues (e.g., federal and state agencies, industry). Conducted under the aegis of the Alliance for Risk Assessment (ARA), the series of three workshops is designed to explore available and evolving methodology through the development and application of case studies and to evolve the methodologies in specific areas raised by the NRC (2009) report.

Conduct of the Workshop

Prior to Workshop 2, a science panel was selected to lead discussions of the proposed methods and case studies during Workshop 2 and build consensus for dose-response assessment methods during the third workshop. The panel was designed to be balanced and reflective of a range of affiliations and perspectives, as well as types of expertise (e.g., biology, risk assessment, modeling); particular effort was made to include people from the NRC's *Science and Decisions* committee and environmental nongovernmental organizations (NGOs). An open nomination process was used and the ARA steering committee reviewed candidates and developed a prioritized list of 27 nominees. Invitations were sent in order of priority, resulting in the following science panel members:

- ▶ *Michael Bolger, U.S. Food and Drug Administration*
- ▶ *James S. Bus, The Dow Chemical Company*
- ▶ *John Christopher, CH2M/Hill*
- ▶ *Rory Conolly, U.S. EPA National Health and Environmental Effects Research Laboratory*
- ▶ *Michael L. Dourson, Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment*
- ▶ *Adam M. Finkel, University of Pennsylvania Law School*²
- ▶ *William Hayes, Indiana Department of Environmental Management (Workshop 2 only)*³
- ▶ *R. Jeffrey Lewis, ExxonMobil Biomedical Sciences, Inc.*
- ▶ *Randall Manning, Georgia Environmental Protection Division (Workshop 3 only)*⁴
- ▶ *Bette Meek, McLaughlin Centre for Population Health Risk Assessment, University of Ottawa*
- ▶ *Paul Moyer, Minnesota Department of Health (Workshop 2 only)*⁵
- ▶ *Gregory Paoli, Risk Sciences International*²
- ▶ *Rita Schoeny, U.S. EPA Office of Water*

²Member of the NRC *Science and Decisions* committee.

³Conflicting job priorities meant that William Hayes needed to withdraw from the panel prior to the third workshop.

⁴Randall Manning was added to the panel as a replacement for William Hayes and Paul Moyer for the third workshop.

⁵Conflicting job priorities meant that Paul Moyer needed to withdraw from the panel prior to the third workshop.

Three rapporteurs took notes during the Workshop and compiled this Workshop Report: Lynne Haber, Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment (TERA) (notes and report); Amy Rosenstein, Consultant (notes and report); and Tiffany Bredfeldt of the Texas Commission on Environmental Quality (TCEQ) (notes only). The draft Workshop report was reviewed by the panel, and panel comments have been incorporated into the final report.

Workshop III Organization

The workshop, held at the offices of Noblis (a workshop sponsor), was organized primarily around three cross-cutting topics identified by the panel: problem formulation, use of mode of action information, and endogenous/background exposure. Discussion of each of these themes was initiated by a presentation by an expert on the topic (see <https://tera.org/Alliance%20for%20Risk/Workshop/WS3/CaseStudiesWS3.html>), followed by panel discussion in the context of case studies when available and relevant. Six new case studies, identified by the panel to address important gaps in methodology, were presented for panel input on the utility of the methods to address specific problem formulations and consideration of areas for additional development. In addition, case study authors provided short updates for panel feedback on five case studies that had been substantially modified since their presentation at the second workshop. A framework for organizing the case study methods that was developed by panel members and workshop participants was presented and briefly discussed. The meeting concluded with a discussion of next steps.

There were several guest presentations during the course of the meeting:

- Rita Schoeny, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. *Experience at EPA in Problem Formulation Relevant to both Ecological and Human Dose-Response Analysis.*
- Bette Meek, University of Ottawa. *“Fit for Purpose” MOA/ Human Relevance Analysis.*
- James Swenberg, University of North Carolina. *Endogenous and Background DNA Adducts as a Means of Understanding Mode of Action (MOA) in the Low End of the Dose Response Curve.*
- Resha Putzrath, U.S. Navy. *Low-Dose Linearity for Noncancer Risks and Dose Additivity for Mixtures.*

The presentations are available at:

<https://tera.org/Alliance%20for%20Risk/Workshop/WS3/CaseStudiesWS3.html>.

PANEL DISCUSSION OF ISSUES

Problem Formulation

Dr. Rita Schoeny of the U.S. EPA introduced the topic with a presentation entitled “Experience at EPA in Problem Formulation Relevant to both Ecological and Human Dose-Response Analysis” (see <https://tera.org/Alliance%20for%20Risk/Workshop/WS3/CaseStudiesWS3.html>). Dr. Schoeny noted that EPA is already doing problem formulation and discussed EPA’s current

initiatives on improving the process. She focused on the need for EPA to do problem formulation in a more formal way to ensure the most useful results. EPA is convening internal meetings on how to use and apply the NRC documents to advance human health risk assessment. Dr. Schoeny presented preliminary results from those meetings in the form of a draft framework for human health risk assessment that builds from NRC (2009) Figure S-1.

Panel discussion following Dr. Schoeny's presentation focused on how problem formulation is actually used in practice and the value of conducting problem formulation. One panel member suggested that public understanding may be aided by improved communication of the issue being addressed and decision context, as well as how the approach chosen relates to the decision context. It is important to ensure that the final decision relates to the problem formulation; it has often been irrelevant to the final decision. A panelist noted that program offices do address problem formulation, while outside the regulatory programs the focus is on hazard. Another panelist suggested that hazard assessments could address this issue up front by describing the problem formulation that came from the program office and motivated the hazard assessment. One panel member pointed out that the problem formulation phase includes considerations of lessons learned from previous similar work, such as: (1) what was the approach; (2) how can one focus resources; (3) how can one draw on previous work; and (4) how can one integrate across species, endpoints, etc. The problem formulation helps one focus on the key elements of the assessment to enhance the efficiency of the assessment process.

Science Panel Discussion Related to Problem Formulation

Panel members addressed the need for the problem formulation to describe the purpose of the assessment and the nature of the answer being sought. Different approaches can be appropriate, depending on the purpose of the assessment. The type of answer being sought might be thought of as the "risk metric," in other words, "What measure of risk is needed?" For example, a cost-benefit analysis requires a different risk metric than a screening assessment. It was noted that the workshop series provides an opportunity to consider a variety of available dose-response methods in the context of the conceptual frameworks proposed by the NRC committee. Screening assessments can use simpler dose-response methods than are needed for in-depth assessments. The approach and depth of the assessment should be "fit for purpose." Assessments with a potentially large economic impact (or widespread exposure of the population) require a greater depth of analysis. Panel members noted that it is important to identify the risk management options up front, since that affects the problem formulation and the need for a risk assessment.

Panel members noted that it is important for the problem formulation to focus up front on the critical issues affecting the hazard assessment. This is particularly important for large assessments. Arraying the data up front and looking for patterns helps in understanding the mode of action and helps one in focusing the assessment effort. Understanding the toxicology of related chemicals also helps in understanding the MOA and points one to the endpoints of interest. However, one panelist noted that the need for protection from court challenges often drives the need to address nontarget endpoints. Another panelist recommended that improved documentation of the process can minimize the need to address other endpoints. Conversely, if a risk management decision is being driven by politics, an in-depth assessment may not be needed. A workshop participant stated that objective criteria (or a particular level of evidence) are needed

to define when further investigation of a potential problem is needed. A panelist suggested that application of the draft framework presented in Dr. Schoeny's talk will drive incremental changes in the way risk assessments are done, with better conduct and communication of the problem formulation. Panel members also noted the utility of early stages of the problem formulation stage in determining how one moves from an early flag of a potential problem to the analysis plan, and the utility of tiered assessments to ensure efficient use of resources.

The panel discussed how to implement improved use of problem formulation and the barriers to implementation. One panelist recommended that formalizing the problem formulation and scoping will help, and that senior managers need to invest the time at the early stages to guide the process. Another panelist recommended that EPA's Risk Assessment Forum require changes in methods, rather than simply recommending them. A panelist also recommended that EPA consider adopting outside assessments. The panelist also stated that EPA understands that not all risk assessments are equal and that it is important to communicate the risk assessment context and problem formulation. Another panel member noted that the approach used depends on the scope and scale of the problem: does the decision have national or regional significance, is there broad exposure to the chemical, or is exposure rare?

Panel members noted that advances in biology are continuing to affect risk assessment methods. One panel member noted the desire to incorporate into decision making an increased understanding of basic biology (e.g., MOA) and to apply new toxicology and biology tools (e.g., "omics") in risk assessment; additional methods development is needed in this area. It is also important not to overpromise; this may also be an issue with novel toxicology methods. Another panel member expressed strong concerns about the potential for incorrect conclusions regarding the MOA, with significant implications for the resulting dose-response assessment.

Panel members discussed the types of problem formulations that require (or benefit from) calculation of a risk-specific dose (RSD). For example, if the hazard quotient (i.e., the ratio between exposure and a value such as the reference dose [RfD] or reference concentration [RfC]) is much lower than a level of concern, then there might be little justification for deriving a RSD, while an RSD would be useful when exposure is in the range of an RfD. One panelist also expressed concern that the concept of a safe dose (or RfD) is poorly defined from the quantitative perspective and therefore has little quantitative meaning. An RSD may also be useful for risk-risk comparisons. The needs of the decision making should define the analysis approach, but the analysis approach also needs to reflect the underlying biology. There was general agreement that it is important to get away from the interpretation of the RfD as a bright line (i.e., high risk above the RfD and absolutely no risk below it). One panelist suggested that it would be useful to identify key scenarios where a RSD is needed. In addition, most current methods are really the effect-specific dose and do not consider overall risk from different endpoints. Another noted that there are alternative methods for calculating risk. For example, EPA's regulation of mercury emissions from electric power plants calculated risk (as a hazard quotient) from these sources in order to determine the best regulatory approach.

Panel discussion also briefly addressed the methods recommended by the NRC (2009) for calculating a RSD. It was noted that the Hattis method (also discussed in more detail as a case study, see below) describes a distribution of thresholds so that a number can be assigned to a defined probability of risk. This approach lends itself to the quantitative analysis of uncertainty.

The panel briefly discussed the utility of this approach but addressed the method in more detail in the context of the case study. Panelists stated that moving away from a threshold/non-threshold approach is in the interests of good science. Panelists also noted that RfDs are associated with different levels of uncertainty, so instances of exceeding the RfD have differing implications.

In considering the different types of assessments (e.g., screening vs. in-depth), a workshop participant encouraged the panel to explicitly note the importance of explaining the context of a decision to the public, so it does not appear that unequal effort was expended for different chemicals. The participant stated that the public communication should also clarify why the level of protection is not compromised when a tiered approach is used. Tiered assessments allow one to first address the problems that are driving decisions and the problems that are important because of public health risks or economics.

Panel members discussed uncertainty in the problem formulation phase. Several noted the importance of qualitative uncertainty analysis, both for default and non-default approaches. The MOA/Human Relevance Framework (MOA/HRF) was designed to aid in identifying key data gaps (Meek et al., 2003; Seed et al., 2005; Boobis et al., 2006). Such descriptions can aid in understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the respective methods. Quantitative uncertainty analysis can follow. A panelist suggested the regulatory impact assessment for EPA's methyl mercury rule as a potential case study on uncertainty analyses. Another panelist suggested that each time an uncertainty is identified the assessment authors should state what kinds of information are necessary to reduce or replace the uncertainty, as a way of moving the science forward. Part of the problem is also that much of the existing toxicity studies are not very useful for risk assessment because they were not designed to address risk assessment issues. Government/industry partnerships would be helpful to address this issue. It was noted that a qualitative uncertainty analysis approach is being crafted as part of an international framework. One panel member noted that qualitative discussion of uncertainty is valuable from the perspective of a small state agency, which will for the most part follow EPA guidance documents unless another state has done some work in an area. A workshop participant suggested early identification of the uncertainties can be used to frame charge questions for peer review.

The panel discussed value of information (VOI) analysis as a formal tool for risk assessment and a way to evaluate the impact of uncertainties. VOI is a formal decision analytic tool that characterizes the relative value (relative to a decision) of reducing various uncertainties in the assessment. VOI analysis is useful in the problem formulation stage to help determine how to focus the assessment and which issues to consider in greater depth. VOI analysis also requires a causal link between obtaining some information and the impact on a *decision* (as opposed to whether additional data will improve the science). A barrier to implementation of VOI analysis has been that it has been considered problematic for assessors to know the stakes of the analysis. Panel members noted a need for discussion between risk assessors and risk managers. However, such discussions need to clearly identify when one is moving into risk management.

The panel discussed how VOI concepts can be applied in the context of the workshop case studies. One panel member suggested panel members could look at the case studies and identify how they address a particular problem. Another noted that in order to do that, the case studies would need to be designed to inform a specific decision. These decisions are not currently

included in the case studies, although they could be. A need for education of risk assessors about problem formulation so that assessors understand how the risk assessment is designed to address a societal problem/need was noted. Panel members noted the need for problem formulation to inform good experimental design, and the need to educate funding agencies on this issue.

The panel discussed the utility of presenting all of the case studies presented at Workshops 2 and 3 in the context of VOI, but no approach to move forward on this idea was identified. Panel members saw an educational value to working with case study authors to provide this framing for their own case studies, rather than a separate group providing that context.

Mode of Action (MOA)

Dr. Bette Meek of the University of Ottawa introduced the topic with a presentation entitled “Fit for Purpose” MOA/Human Relevance Analysis” (see <https://tera.org/Alliance%20for%20Risk/Workshop/WS3/CaseStudiesWS3.html>). Dr. Meek stressed that risk assessments should focus on MOA early in the process in order to increase the efficiency and utility of assessments, particularly in light of the many unevaluated chemicals in the marketplace. She noted the importance of MOA analysis for moving towards predictive assessments and using the new tools developed as part of toxicity testing in the 21st century. Rather than thinking primarily in terms of defaults, she recommended a change in paradigm, with assessors moving towards early assimilation of the data in a MOA context. She noted that MOA analyses need to be rigorously conducted according to established criteria for determining the weight of evidence. Such analyses can help move the science forward, while inadequately supported MOA analyses are no better than default (and may be more problematic). She also noted that the need to evaluate data-poor chemicals is increasing the use of (quantitative) structure activity relationship [(Q)SAR] analyses, and that there is a need for an understanding of the mechanistic underpinnings of toxicity in order to develop and apply such models. Dr. Meek noted that the emphasis on defaults has focused risk assessment on being appropriately health-protective, but with limited predictive capacity based on an understanding of how chemicals induce their effects. She recommended that part of the initial public problem formulation should include an assimilated overview of the relevant data and a proposal for the process to be used for the assessment, taking into account resource limitations and any relevant legislative mandates.

Panel members discussed with Dr. Meek issues related to implementation of her recommendations. Dr. Meek suggested that one barrier to a greater focus on MOA is the ease of using default approaches relative to the additional thinking required to address MOA. However, she also stated that while default approaches are presumed to be public health protective, this is supported principally on the basis of empirical rather than mechanistic underpinnings and, as a result, limits the utility of the output to consider, for example, risks associated with chemicals that act by similar modes of action. Panel members raised concerns about the additional time and data needed for an MOA analysis. For example, an MOA focus using more data-rich chemicals to inform assessments of data-poor chemicals is more time consuming in early stages, but provides considerable efficiencies in the assessments of like chemicals and prediction of effects for those with limited datasets. This is clearly preferred over focusing solely on the lowest effect level in the longest term study, which draws on a very limited subset of the available data and is unhelpful as a basis for application in a broader context to other situations or chemicals. Thus, hazard *characterization* is preferred over hazard *identification*. The former

is a more integrative approach with a focus on MOA, considering the relationships among effects observed, across species, strains, and in both sexes, while the latter merely identifies targets. Panel members also noted that MOA can inform testing needs, and there is a need to modify guideline study designs to include MOA considerations. This is currently underway through OECD (the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, which has previously led the development of harmonized test guidelines) in coordination with national and international organizations. One panel member noted that a screening paradigm could address whether an MOA evaluation will result in a better answer than the default, addressing whether there is an incentive to develop the relevant information.

In response to a panelist's question about concerns raised by some that an increased MOA focus may increase the level of uncertainty, Dr. Meek stated that it is important to characterize the uncertainties associated with *both* default and non-default approaches. Knowing more about the sources of uncertainty does not mean that uncertainty is increased; it is just being described better. Characterizing the uncertainty also allows one to identify what data are needed in order to meet criteria for application of MOA-based approaches. Dr. Meek expressed preference for basing assessments on the most certain rather than the most conservative data, but then characterizing the uncertainties in bounds on the data. She noted, however, that quantitative uncertainty analysis is rare for dose-response assessments, although it is more common for exposure assessments.

Science Panel Discussion Related to Mode of Action

The panel discussed how MOA can contribute to the risk assessment process. One panelist considered MOA as a prominent aspect of a "unified approach" to risk assessment as described by the NRC (2009), and noted the need to link the MOA to the problem formulation. This linkage would identify how an understanding of MOA affects the results of the risk assessment and the implications for risk management. For example, the shape of the dose-response curve may have a large impact on the expected risk at specified doses and therefore can have a large financial impact. Panel members also noted the utility of bringing MOA thinking to the consideration of combined exposures and screening assessments. For example, structural alerts have been used for years in the context of genotoxicity evaluations. Predictive tools can also be helpful in resolving issues for data-rich chemicals. MOA analysis requires multidisciplinary input.

The panel agreed that MOA analysis is a way to think about information and to focus resources where they will be most useful in resolving issues. It is useful as an aid in designing toxicity testing and in focusing on what is important in a risk assessment. Assimilation of the data includes such considerations as the doses at which effects are seen (relative to human exposure) and the implications of dose-dependent transitions.

The panel discussed how a MOA perspective can be useful for different levels of depth of an assessment. One panelist recommended that the panel emphasize that the consideration of MOA, molecular initiating events, and adverse outcome pathways are all related concepts. There is a continuum of approaches for applying MOA. MOA judgments, in particular for groups of closely related compounds, can be made based on the weight of evidence, including structural alerts, even if data are insufficient to complete all aspects of the human relevance framework.

The molecular initiating event provides information about hazard. Panelists noted that the MOA is based on a limited number of rate-limiting and dose-limiting key events that inform the shape of the dose-response curve. The MOA may not be a linear pathway and can include other contributing events and competing pathways. Knowledge of the mode of action also contributes to understanding of factors affecting human variability, such as genetic susceptibilities and modulating factors, which impact on dose-response. Consideration of MOA is important both for assessments based on animal data and for those based on human data. For the former, MOA informs issues related to human relevance (which increases the importance of MOA); for the latter, it provides insight as to susceptible subgroups. One panel member suggested that MOA-related thinking can also be used to consider physiological processes that cause an organism not to respond following chemical exposure (i.e., a no observed effects level [NOEL] MOA), including considerations such as kinetics, metabolism and homeostatic mechanisms. A workshop participant suggested that this approach could be used to predict a dose corresponding to a *de minimis* risk level.

The panel noted the need for intelligent design of toxicity studies rather than investigating every possible effect. Modern toxicology methods such as genomics can aid in moving from high-dose testing while also aiding in the understanding of events leading to apical effects.

The panel also discussed uncertainty in the context of MOA considerations. From a qualitative perspective, it is important to consider the uncertainties in both classical and newer approaches, not just focus on uncertainties related to newer tools. One panel member asked whether it would be possible to set predetermined data quality objectives for false positives and false negatives for the use of *in vitro* data. A workshop participant replied that the mathematical tools are available, but a quantitative understanding of the biology is insufficient for applying such methods. However, Bayesian and value of information analyses are being used to address this type of question, at least in a research context. Panelists noted that methods for safe doses include areas of uncertainty, and one could bound dose-response assessments based on consideration of the relevant uncertainties. Such considerations need to recognize differences in the uncertainty factors relating to uncertainty and those relating to variability. It is also important to consider what elements are contributing to uncertainty and that the uncertainty associated with different safe dose values (e.g., RfDs for different chemicals) differs depending on the database and the associated uncertainty factors. Workshop participants noted that individual uncertainty factors (UFs) are generally based on approximately the 90th percentile for the relevant extrapolation based on an empirical analysis of observational data, and multiplying UFs can compound conservatism. Panelists commented that the result of this process is that the level of protectiveness of the RfD is, essentially, unknown.

Endogenous and Background Exposures

Dr. James Swenberg of the University of North Carolina provided some background by describing work done in his laboratory using stable isotopic labeling, which is an approach that allows one to distinguish between adducts resulting from endogenous and exogenous exposures. He noted that, in the absence of endogenous exposure, DNA adduct formation is linear at doses as low as can be measured, and he expects the dose-response for adducts to be linear at low doses, reaching zero at zero dose. If there is endogenous production of the same adduct, the adduct level at zero dose is nonzero. Unlike most types of DNA adducts, there is always a

background level of mutations; mutation frequency is not zero at zero dose. The background mutation frequency reflects the summation of mutations arising from endogenous DNA damage that occurs in all cells. Most mutagenesis studies have focused on hazard identification, and more information is needed on the dose response for mutations. DNA adducts are a biomarker of exposure, while mutations are a biomarker of effect. Dr. Swenberg recommended that the point of departure (POD) should be the inflection point where mutations increase above background. He considers the background to be a true biological threshold rather than reflecting nonlinearity that cannot be distinguished from the control due to variability. This POD might represent an exposure that could be used with appropriate uncertainty factors (or Chemical Specific Adjustment Factors [CSAFs]) to extrapolate from the experimental animal model to humans and to protect susceptible populations, similarly to what is done currently.

A panel member noted the relevance of a recent publication from an ILSI (International Life Sciences Institute) Health and Environmental Sciences Institute (HESI) committee on integrating DNA adduct data into risk assessment (Jarabek et al., 2009). That committee agreed that there is a high bar for the data requirements for using the dose response for DNA adducts as the basis of a risk assessment. One needs to demonstrate causality and that the adduct is promutagenic, persistent and present in tissue of concern. The HESI panel concluded that levels of exposure that could be considered acceptable can be determined based on adduct levels when there is no endogenous source of an adduct, but this determination cannot be done if the adduct is formed endogenously.

Science Panel Discussion Related to Endogenous and Background Exposures

Panel members had varying perspectives on the impact of endogenous levels on the resulting risk assessment. There was general agreement that the implications of a small number of adducts is different if the endogenous levels are zero than if the body endogenously creates 10,000 identical adducts. However, some panelists considered the decision in the latter scenario (i.e., that a few adducts on top of 10,000 of the same adduct from endogenous sources is a trivial addition) to contain risk management elements (because a decision on the significance of the additional adducts has already been made). Other panelists emphasized the importance of considering variability in endogenous levels, and they considered minimal increases over endogenous levels to be indistinguishable from variability. They noted that even for a given individual, normal daily activity—not including external exposures—can result in an increase in adduct formation. This variability can be characterized, and the implications of the variability can be evaluated. A panelist suggested that one could look at whether exposure is significantly different from the variability in endogenous levels.

Several panelists stated that the key issue is the implication of the endogenous exposure on effect. If the endogenous exposure results in an effect, then the addition of even a few adducts or a small amount of damage is biologically meaningful.⁶ Thus, it is possible that even a small

⁶A panel member provided the following postmeeting comment about how the Pottenger et al. case study on background/endogenous damage could inform the discussion: “According to Swenberg, DNA adducts resulting from an external exposure [to vinyl chloride] of approximately 10 ppm result in adduct loads that blend in with background. If one assumed a linear risk assessment model for a point of departure of 10 ppm, and using the cancer slope factor derived for vinyl chloride from animal data, the expected number of angiosarcomas of the liver could be

amount of exposure on top of endogenous levels could be above a threshold. Conversely, if endogenous levels are below a threshold, the addition of a few additional adducts would not affect the cell. A workshop participant added that non-threshold modeling might be considered if endogenous exposure is near a threshold, even if the exposure is below the threshold, because a small increment could have an impact. Using a linear non-threshold approach implies that there is the same increment of risk for each increment of dose, but if there is a threshold then the risk implications of an increment of dose depend on where the endogenous levels are relative to the threshold. It was noted that the issue of endogenous exposure is relevant to evaluating risk both from DNA-reactive chemicals and for noncancer endpoints.

Panel members noted the difficulty of addressing the issue of endogenous exposure in a risk assessment context and the absence of a clear consistent approach. Instead of generic answers, a decision tree is needed to aid in consideration of endogenous exposure on a case-specific basis using the data available for that chemical.

One panelist stated that if one applies linear non-threshold extrapolation based on endogenous adducts or from exposure to the natural carcinogens in food, the results would be inconsistent with life. This suggests an inconsistency with an assumption of risk assessment on issues such as the extrapolation approach or treatment of endogenous adducts. Another panelist noted that another problematic assumption or component of the calculation could be the actual value of the slope factor.

The panel also addressed background to some degree, although not as thoroughly as endogenous exposures were addressed. Following the NRC (2009) approach, the panel distinguished between background exposure (not explicitly defined by the panel but defined in other contexts as exposure that results from sources other than the subject of the risk assessment) and background response (a response of the same nature due to a cause other than the exposure of interest, such as decreased lung function due to asthma). One panelist suggested that issues related to background exposure can be considered in terms of the background exposure to the same chemical or exposure to similarly acting or interacting chemicals. The former issue can be addressed by comparisons with concurrent control groups (which presumably would have the same background exposure), and the latter issue can be addressed using existing mixtures risk assessment guidance. Background response is a more challenging issue, requiring an understanding of the cause and dose-response characteristics for that background. For example, a panelist noted that consideration of the implications of low-level exposures on top of background response is more complicated as the background rate increases in either the animal test population or the human population. Another panelist recommended caution in extrapolating information on background response from animal studies. The panelist noted that certain strains of rodents have a high and variable background response in certain tissues, making the identification of critical effect particularly problematic for studies in which those tissues are affected. The panel did not further address issues related to background response.

calculated for the entire US population. Since it is known that angiosarcomas are rare (approximately 30-40 cases/year), and the animal and human tumor responses are highly coherent, if much higher levels of tumor response are predicted for the US population, such a finding would highly inform the applicability of low-dose linear models in predicting real risk of DNA-reaction and genotoxic substances like vinyl chloride.”

Panel members also noted that there are broader policy issues involving value judgments about the implications of background exposure and whether it is better at the societal level to expose people who have high or low background exposure (to the same chemical). One can think of the issue as whether it is better to have a few people with higher risk, or more people with smaller risk (because the total exposure has been spread out across more people). This issue is encountered in, for example, radiation cleanup scenarios. Panelists noted that there is no consensus on the resolution to this issue.

The panel concluded that the same consideration as discussed in the context of endogenous exposure applies to background exposures, that is, that one needs to consider background exposure relative to the effect caused and relative to a threshold. The implications of background response were not further addressed.

Use of Defaults

The panel discussed issues related to use of default approaches and parameters as well as the use of alternatives to defaults. One panelist noted the approach that was used by the U.S. Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) when it adopted the first risk assessment based on a physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model, which used rigorous, structured and logical criteria to compare the PBPK and the default allometric approaches. The panelist expressed concern that EPA responded to the NRC (1994) report by stating that checklists of questions are not possible or desirable, whereas many others believe such criteria are straightforward to develop and highly useful. The panelist also expressed concern about EPA's statements of "data first, defaults second," stating that the actual choice is not between data and defaults, but among various alternative models/assumptions (defaults and others), all of which require data but interpret the data in different ways. Other panel members agreed that the choice is not between data and defaults. Instead, these panelists described the extent of reliance on critically evaluated, more specific, and robust information related to chemical-specific or compound-related mode of action, rather than generic approaches based on less-specific generic empirical analysis. The first panelist stated that (some) defaults are based on decades of good science (e.g., the assumption that effects seen in animals are relevant to humans), and stated that alternative models are only as good as the theory and evidence supporting them, objecting to the term "more data-informed." The panelist reiterated the NRC (2009) statement that non-default approaches should be "clearly superior" in order to be used instead of defaults.

Other panel members suggested that areas of disagreement are smaller than may be apparent and that the case for non-default approaches is sometimes over-emphasized in an attempt to move the risk assessment community forward. These panelists expressed the desire that people understand the underlying bases for defaults, and that uncertainties in defaults are understood and characterized. There are times that defaults are appropriately applied, but the aim is to think about their application, not apply them by rote. One panelist stated that the aim is to avoid the application of *unsuitable* defaults, and it is also not appropriate to discard defaults by rote. Another suggested that the phrase "increasingly data-informed approaches" (reflecting approaches for use of data within analytical frameworks), or perhaps the phrase "continuum reflecting different degrees of inference from the data," might be better than the word "default," because either of the phrases more aptly capture how risk assessors synthesize the available data.

Panel members also stated that it is desirable to apply chemical-specific and biologically relevant data when relevant and appropriate and that it is useful to identify barriers to that goal. They stated that transparent communication is needed regarding uncertainties in both default and non-default approaches. Clear criteria for use of non-default approaches and for evaluation of data quality have been developed by international organizations and need to be applied. Panelists specifically noted the IPCS (2005) guidance for chemical-specific adjustment factors (CSAFs), EPA's guidance for relative source contribution (U.S. EPA, 2000), and the MOA/human relevance framework (Meek et al., 2003; Seed et al., 2005; Boobis et al., 2006). Criteria may still be needed in other areas. One panelist emphasized the importance of management leadership, so that less experienced staff can learn to think about issues such as mode of action and how to focus on the critical issues.

Panelists noted that it can be appropriate to make a science policy choice to use default even if the weight of evidence supports other approaches, but that the reason for the decision should be clear. A panelist stated that the precautionary nature of defaults means that the use of more chemical-specific data is likely to result in higher (less conservative) toxicity values (e.g., RfDs or RfCs), and it is hard to communicate this concept to the public, who have often been told that smaller numbers are better. Workshop participants also noted that the understanding of biology has evolved since early defaults were developed, and this greater understanding is informing the usefulness (or not) of non-default methods.

FRAMEWORK

Lynne Haber of TERA presented and described the ARA Dose Response Framework, available at <https://tera.org/Alliance%20for%20Risk/Workshop/Framework/ProblemFormulation.html>. The framework was developed by panel members and workshop participants as a way of organizing the case studies and methods, in order to help identify gaps in methods and to aid risk assessors in identifying useful tools for different problem formulations. The framework builds on the general structure of the frameworks presented in the NRC (2009) report (Figures S-1 and 5-8). The framework is applicable to different general problem formulation needs, including qualitative, screening and in-depth assessments. Applicable case studies are linked to each of the elements in the Framework (Endpoint Assessment, Mode of Action, Vulnerable Subpopulations and Endogenous Exposures) and/or to Dose-Response Method Selection, to provide ready access to examples of methods that the risk assessor can review and potentially use to assess risks in specific situations or settings. Dr. Haber noted that the methods currently listed in the framework are not exhaustive and some of the areas where additional tools could be developed are shown.

In general, the panel members found the framework to be very helpful, although it could be developed further. For example, it might be possible to expand the framework, providing linkages to existing guidance or case studies. It was recommended that criteria for inclusion in the framework be considered. One panel member suggested that the first frame of the framework be modified to include an iterative feedback loop. The process would begin with asking the risk manager about the options and then ensure that the risk assessment addressed the initial question. Another panelist noted that some of that sort of feedback is included in the full Figure S-1 of NRC (2009).

ADDITIONAL METHODS NEEDED

The panel briefly discussed additional methods that should be added to the framework. A panelist noted that the framework spells out issues to consider, but one purpose of the case studies is to illustrate the thinking process that is used. As noted in the Executive Summary, methods mentioned included:

- More is needed on combined exposures. There is a recently published WHO IPCS framework report that will be helpful in providing and framing appropriate case studies.
- A case study on value of information and its use at an early stage of problem formulation would be useful. A workshop participant offered to provide relevant case studies, including both formal case studies and simple decision trees. One panelist stated that the process used for EPA's arsenic regulation illustrates the utility of considering value of information. Risk management options were identified up front, then the benefits and costs associated with those options were considered
- A case study that illustrates an entire risk assessment, from problem formulation to conclusion (including risk management), would be useful.
- A case study on *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation would be useful. ILSI is doing work in this area.
- The ARA Dose-Response Framework for case studies could point to examples outside of this compendium of case studies.

Panel members disagreed on the utility of expanding on the Hattis straw man approach. Some saw a utility to developing additional risk values with the approach and comparing them with classical methods, while others saw that as simply expanding an existing case study. A panel member also suggested that it would be useful to bring in a risk management perspective on issues such as the implications of exceeding an RfD.

NEXT STEPS

Several next steps were recommended. These include:

- Publication of a short peer-reviewed journal article capturing key results and lessons learned from the workshop series, illustrated by case studies (e.g., in text boxes), and pointing the reader to the framework for organizing the dose-response methods and case studies. The panel favored the journal *Environmental Health Perspectives*.
- Developing an evergreen approach, including panel review of methods on an annual or semi-annual basis, leading to updating the framework for organizing the dose-response methods and case studies.
- A standing committee should be formed to approve additions to/revisions of case studies to the framework.

- Further dissemination of the workshop results to the risk assessment community is needed, including presentations at professional society meetings and to influential individuals and groups. Specifically, there was significant support for a dedicated poster session at the Society of Toxicology annual meeting. Additional targeted presentations were recommended to such groups as EPA's Risk Assessment Forum (e.g., the EPA dose-response group working on how to address the NRC recommendations) and the Science Advisory Board.

The Dose-Response Advisory Committee will finalize proposals and options regarding the next steps and report back to the panel as these next steps will affect the content of the manuscript.

One objective of the manuscript is to highlight the framework as a way of organizing and providing access to a compendium of methods. Another objective is to communicate key results from the workshop series, addressing and clarifying issues raised by NRC (2009). It was noted that additional thinking on some issues will be needed beyond what was accomplished at the workshop, and one challenge will be to write the text so that it makes a meaningful contribution.

The panel identified several points that the manuscript should address, as listed here:

- That many different problem formulations exist, and there are many approaches to dose-response assessment.
- How to incorporate VOI in problem formulation. Because value of information was not discussed by the panel in detail and not addressed in any case study, the manuscript would acknowledge the importance of VOI, but not focus on it. Instead, it was highly recommended that a case study on VOI be included in a future iteration of an evergreen product.
- The importance of early communication with risk managers and stakeholders of the risk assessment plan and how the plan relates to the problem formulation.
- Utility of incorporation of MOA into analyses and moving to more data-informed approaches. For example, MOA-based analyses, such as the chlorpyrifos case study, can help to address broader issues regarding the implications of human variability for chemicals that act via a similar MOA.
- Framing the criteria for moving to increasingly data-informed approaches.
- The need for transparency.
- Clarifying terminology regarding endogenous and background exposure and identification of issues to consider in those contexts
- The impact of endogenous levels of DNA adducts (DNA is not "clean").
- Identifying which of the case study methods might have utility in certain situations, but are not useful in other situations.

- That the case studies are useful for the manuscript to the degree that they illustrate broader issues. For example, the chlorpyrifos and endogenous adducts case studies illustrate ways to address some fundamental issues.
- That the biologically and statistically oriented parts of the risk assessment community have different perspectives on issues related to dose-response and the implications of MOA.
- That the proximity of exposure to an estimate of a safe dose may drive the need for a risk-specific dose for a chemical with a threshold MOA. However, it was noted that it is difficult to calculate risk-specific doses that appropriately reflect biology for chemicals that do not interact with DNA, or even to accurately estimate risk-specific doses for chemicals that do interact with DNA, in light of the large degree of extrapolation below the data and uncertainties regarding the shape of the dose-response curve.

The panel also provided some initial thoughts regarding the manuscript structure:

- The article would begin with introductory text describing the process for the workshop series, participants and objectives.
- The text could provide a roadmap of steps to take in an assessment and why. The text can provide the concepts, which then can be illustrated using text boxes of case studies as examples.
- Lessons learned can be highlighted.
- The workshop rapporteurs will provide an outline for the manuscript. This would be followed by a panel conference call. The workshop report and Executive Summary would provide a basis for panel members to develop the manuscript text.

CONCLUSIONS

The workshop series has succeeded in bringing together a broad range of stakeholders to address dose-response issues. The panelists and workshop participants found value in various aspects of the NRC (2009) report, including some areas that initially generated some skepticism in the risk assessment community, but found that other recommendations of the NRC report were not easily implemented. The workshop series has produced a compendium of case studies that address dose-response methods related to different problem formulations. The workshop series also helped further the integration of problem formulation and MOA into risk assessment as recommended by the NRC (2009).

CASE STUDY DISCUSSIONS

Six new case studies, identified by the panel to address important gaps in methodology, were presented for panel input on the utility of the methods to address specific problem formulations and consideration of areas for additional development. In addition, case study authors provided

short updates for panel feedback on five case studies that had been substantially modified since their presentation at the second workshop.

It was noted that the straw man and biomonitoring equivalents case studies both present a number of areas for possible enhancements that could be addressed in an evergreen workshop process.

Table 1. Workshop III – Summary of New Case Study Discussions

<i>New Case Studies</i>	
Lead Dose-Response Relationship for Effect on Children’s IQ	Presented by: Carrington C.
<p>The panel supported carrying this method forward. The panel recommended that the case study be modified to identify the problem formulation, specifically how the analysis helps to support a decision. The panel also recognized that a key limitation to the assessment was that only pooled data were available to the case study author and that it would be useful if the epidemiology community would make the raw data available for additional analyses. The panel recommended that the author add text regarding what types of additional research could be done with the raw data.</p>	
Quantitative Assessment of Sensitivity and Variability in Humans: Modeling the Effects of Low-Dose Exposure to Dietary Residues of Chlorpyrifos	Presented by Juberg, D.R.; Price, P.
<p>The panel supported carrying this method forward as an illustration of how data can be used to derive chemical-specific adjustment factors (CSAFs). The panel recommended that the case study emphasize that <i>in vitro</i> information on kinetic variability cannot be used directly to calculate CSAFs; one needs to use those data to calculate the impact on tissue <i>dose</i>. Potential enhancements noted would be to address cumulative risk using such resources as market basket surveys or data on biomonitoring. The panel suggested that the authors link more of the discussion to the NRC report and explain how the key case study conclusions address issues raised in the NRC report. For example, the case study addresses the concerns raised in Chapters 4 or 5 of the NRC report about the adequacy of a factor of 10 for the intraspecies uncertainty factor. The case study also challenges the idea that a background response for the apical effect would linearize the dose-response. An important result was the finding that dietary exposure is expected to have a very small impact on a precursor key event (cholinesterase in the blood), indicating an even smaller effect on an apical response. The panel also noted that it would be useful to include in the case study information on the status and nature of the related EPA review.</p>	

<p>COS and TCB Case Studies Comparing Two Human Health Noncancer Risk Assessment Models: BMDS and Straw Man</p>	<p>Presented by: Greco S.L.; Hattis, D.; Lynch, M.K.</p>
<p>The panel supported carrying this method forward as a useful approach for calculating risk-specific doses for noncancer endpoints. The panel asked for clarification of the contents of the database of analogous chemicals that was used to derive the distributions. Transparency in that information and clear delineation of uncertainties is important for acceptance of the method. A workshop participant noted that the database used for the distribution could be refined based on an understanding of the MOA, and panel members noted that results of research on chemical-specific adjustment factors (CSAFs) could be used to bound the distributions. There was considerable panel discussion about the utility of comparing the straw man analysis with an existing RfD, since the straw man risk value would change if different measures of the response level or confidence bounds were used. Some panelists saw such comparisons as very important to understanding the implications of the approach and for pushing for a definition of a risk management goal (e.g., 1/100,000 affected with 95% confidence). Others saw a need to focus on the merits of the method itself and suggested masking the chemical names. A suggested finesse was to include the RfD comparison in an appendix to the report. Other suggestions included comparing the results using this method with the results achieved when applying standard scaling to animal data, and clarifying the reason why severity was not included in the straw man analysis (because there were not sufficient data to do this analysis). Panel members recommended that the analysis be conducted for additional chemicals, and one panel member volunteered to write criteria for the choice of case studies. Additional research was suggested on the implications of the choice of response level (e.g., 1/100,000) and of the confidence limit. Overall, the panel expressed support for the method and a need for a broader buy-in by the risk assessment community of this sort of probabilistic approach. Once there is general support of the method, it is expected that people will generate additional useful data on distributions.</p>	
<p>Risk-Risk Comparison: Comparative Risk for Use of Perchloroethylene (Perc) or N-propyl Bromide (NPB) in Dry Cleaning</p>	<p>Presented by: Clewell, H. Co-author: Finkel, A.</p>
<p>The panel supported carrying this method forward (including information that was in the presentation and not the case study summary) as a useful beginning to addressing a challenging problem. Panel members noted that strengths of the approach include the use of an overall data array and early assimilation of the data. They noted that the general approach (particularly as illustrated in the presentation) has more applications than solely in risk-risk comparisons. For example, the approach could be used to evaluate the impact of various decisions on the final degree of risk reduction and to aid in prioritizing work in a broader assessment; it would be useful to note these advantages. The authors noted that the ultimate goal would be to end up with distributions of relative risk, and that probabilistic analysis or expert elicitation could be used to achieve that goal. The panel requested that additional information be provided</p>	

<p>explaining why the BMD was chosen for the comparison, rather than the BMDL. Panel members also noted the utility of leveraging resources, as was done in this case study, with multiple agencies and assessments using the same work on hazard identification.</p>	
<p>Risk Assessment of Exposure to Trihalomethane Drinking Water Disinfection By-products. Use of Biomonitoring Equivalents and Biomonitoring Data From NHANES</p>	<p>Presented by: Aylward L.L. Co-authors: Hays, S.M.; Kirman, C.R.; Becker R.A.</p>
<p>The panel supported carrying this method forward because it demonstrates how biomonitoring results can be interpreted in a risk assessment context, and it demonstrates the utility of biomonitoring data that integrate across all exposures. In addition, this case study addresses combined exposures. The panel suggested that language be added regarding the fact that probabilistic approaches are not included in the case study but could be included if the distributions could be populated. A panel member noted that the MOA for tumor formation differs for chloroform (cytotoxicity) and the brominated trihalomethanes (mutagenicity), and suggested that the potential for mutagenicity in fatty liver be considered. The panel recommended that case study authors should be more explicit about whether this assessment approach is conservative, both qualitatively and, to the extent possible, quantitatively. The authors should note that the model could adjust dose metrics for sensitive populations and therefore could address variability in the population. The question was raised whether the same approach would be appropriate for more persistent chemicals, and the authors were encouraged to address the relevant issues in the text. The panel also considered it important to describe how results from biomonitoring would feed into other types of chemical assessments. Panel members encouraged the authors to place the case study in the context of the WHO combined exposures framework and to consider whether the approach would be appropriate with combined exposure for more persistent chemicals or biomarkers.</p>	
<p>Background/Endogenous Damage: Considerations for Dose-Response and Risk Assessment</p>	<p>Presented by: Pottenger L.H. Co-authors: Bus, J.S.; Swenberg, J.A.</p>
<p>The panel supported carrying this method forward, but recommended clarifying terminology. Panel members noted that DNA adducts are biomarkers of exposure and may represent a key event, but that interaction with DNA is not a rate-limiting key event. Adduct formation may be reversible. Mutation is the most important key event for a mutagenic mode of action. The panel considered how the background mutation rate can help inform a risk management decision about a safe level for a carcinogen; one panelist suggested that the background mutation rate may be associated with a background tumor rate in a 2-stage cancer model. A panelist recommended including aflatoxin in the case study because the aflatoxin adduct is unique. The case study authors noted that they would like to do a comparison of predicted tumor incidence for their case study with the actual number in a population.</p>	

<i>Revised Case Studies</i>	
BBDR Model for Respiratory Tract Carcinogenicity of Inhaled Formaldehyde	Presented by: Clewell, H. Co-authors: Allen, B.; Conolly, R.; Haney, J.; Kester, J.
<p>In Workshop 2, the panel agreed with the authors that it would be useful to modify the model to include the role of endogenous formaldehyde. The panel supporting the ongoing research plan, including an uncertainty analysis, comparing the various approaches to one another and to the default-driven approaches of EPA. More data is forthcoming to quantify the endogenous level of DNA adducts in human noses, providing another kind of benchmark. The panel agreed that this would be useful in the context of the computational fluid dynamics model. From a value of information (VOI) perspective, the panel noted a clear value, and that the results will aid in the risk assessment.</p>	
Assessment of Low-Dose Dose-Response Relationships (Non-linear or Linear) for Genotoxicity, Focused on Induction of Mutations and Clastogenic Effects	Presented by: Moore, M., Pottenger, L. Co-authors: Zeiger, E.; Zhou, T.
<p>In Workshop 2, the panel recommended that the authors enhance the study by conducting a MOA analysis for mutation and by conducting formal statistical tests specifically comparing the tumor dose-response slope with that of the mutation dose-response slope. In the MOA analysis, focusing on recent data, the authors found supporting data for some key events, but there was a lack of data for other events. A panel member suggested that in the future, it would be important to match the low-dose response for mutations with the dose-response assessment for tumors. However, the authors noted that there might not be enough low-dose data, and the panel agreed that this is an important point to stress in the case study write-up. Panel members noted it is important to be clear about where data exist and where they do not; a qualitative VOI analysis could be conducted related to the data gaps. The panel encouraged the study authors to think about identifying the critical data gaps and identifying what is driving the process. A panel member suggested that the authors think mechanistically about whether a hockey stick dose-response shape is due to a fundamental biological nonlinearity or due to background noise.</p>	
Applying Linear Low-Dose Extrapolation From Benchmark Dose for Noncancer Risk Assessment	Presented by: Kroner, O.; Haber, L. Co-author: Hertzberg, R.
<p>Based on panel feedback during Workshop 2, the case study was enhanced to include linear extrapolation using probit, log-dose transformation. Only 4 of the 25 chemicals evaluated for the previous workshop had sufficient data to apply the probit analysis, and the results were inconsistent. Therefore, the case study authors concluded that the method has limited applicability, in particular based on the restrictive data requirements. However, a panel member suggested that the analysis could be done if less restrictive criteria for data adequacy were used.</p>	

<p>The panel suggested that the authors write up the case study to illustrate that the study attempted to follow the recommendations from the NRC (2009) report. The write-up should also emphasize the limits of the methods as well as their applicability and what was learned from the case study, but that this method does not move the science forward.</p>	
<p>Framework for Evaluating Alternative Temporal Patterns of Exposure for Risk Characterization</p>	<p>Presented by: Haber, L. Co-authors: Parker, A.; Maier, A.; Haney, J.; Kaden, D.A.; Carrier, R.; Sweeney, L.; Craft, E.; Hertzberg, R.</p>
<p>In Workshop 2, the panel recommended evaluation of additional chemicals, revision of the case study for clarity, and consideration of the overlap with occupational risk assessment approaches. The authors expanded the framework and developed generic kinetic models to provide rough guidance for many other chemicals, but did not specifically apply the framework to additional chemicals. The latter step is planned for chemicals for which the mechanisms are known and which have PBPK models. An additional question arose regarding how to include multiple mechanisms of repair. While the current model considers repair rates qualitatively, it would be an enhancement to consider repair rates quantitatively. The panel concluded that the overall method needs validation.</p>	
<p>Data Fusion Methods (Petroleum Hydrocarbons)</p>	<p>Presented by: Mohapatra, A.K.; Sadiq R. Co-authors: Zargar, A.; Islam, S.; Dyck, R.</p>
<p>In Workshop 2, the panel recommended that the authors provide additional information on the practical applications of data fusion methodologies. The case study authors provided examples for Workshop 3, but panel members felt that the usefulness of the methodology still needs to be more clearly demonstrated and recommended that the authors clarify how this method offers advantages to chemical risk assessors. The panel recommended that the utility of the method would be illustrated best by applying it to a problem that other methods cannot resolve. The method is particularly useful for addressing issues with a hierarchical aspect, deep uncertainty, and conflict, such as where there is conflict between animal toxicity data and epidemiology data. Breaking the overall approach into smaller intermediate steps (e.g., focusing on only interspecies differences or utility of <i>in vitro</i> data) would make it easier to communicate with the risk assessment community and gain acceptance of the methods. It was suggested that the authors put the work in the context of data and issues that risk assessors are already familiar with, so they can understand the benefits of the approach. The method may be useful for ecological risk assessment, using information on receptor species to evaluate the overall effect on the ecosystem.</p>	

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